

DESIGN OF AN INTELLIGENT LIGHTING AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR NIGERIAN CLASSROOMS

***Ezetoha F. C. and Nwokeke A. O.**

Department of Computer Engineering Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Oko, Anambra State

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18877529>

Abstract: *The challenge of providing sufficient lighting in Nigerian classrooms is exacerbated by inconsistent electricity supply and inadequate architectural design. This study addresses the integration of smart artificial lighting and energy management technologies in enhancing classroom illumination, optimizing energy usage, and mitigating health risks associated with poor lighting conditions. The objective of the work was to create a reliable system capable of maintaining illumination level at 300 lux when natural light is insufficient and to automatically switch OFF lights and electrical appliances when there is no occupant in classroom. Top down design approach was adopted for the hardware and software design respectively. Proteus 8.4 software was used for authentication of the hardware design. The major components of the system were 3,5KVA solar inverter system, Arduino Nano board, light sensor, ultrasonic sensor, dimmable LED panel lights, transformers, discrete components, relays and sockets. The system was successfully designed and its main function is to maintain illumination level at 300 lux when natural light is insufficient during normal classroom activities and 200 lux during presentations, and to automatically switch OFF lights and electrical appliances when nobody is in the classroom. It is recommended that this design should be implemented and used in classrooms in Nigeria in order to provide adequate illumination, optimize energy usage, and mitigate health risks associated with poor lighting conditions.*

Keywords: *Classroom, Illumination, Intelligent Lighting, Energy Management, System.*

Introduction

Lighting is essential for the well-being of humans, as it influences activities ranging from navigation to communication. Light is crucial not only for daily tasks but also for health, mood, and overall well-being. Research has demonstrated that lighting conditions can have significant physiological and psychological effects, impacting everything from social behavior to mental health. In fact, inadequate exposure to natural daylight was estimated to have contributed to depression in about 0.8% of the world's population in 2007 (Halliwell et al., 2007). In classroom environments, adequate lighting is vital for occupant comfort and learning achievements. Classroom lighting is typically a combination of

natural and artificial sources to achieve optimal illumination levels for general tasks or specific functions (Ezetoha & Chukwulobe, 2020). A well-lit classroom maintains an ambient illuminance of 300 lux (Tigerlight, 2013), achieved predominantly through natural daylight, supplemented by artificial lighting when necessary. Adequate classroom light contributes to learning success; it helps maintain attention levels and it is necessary for establishment of a state of “flow” (Dyck, 2002) and improvement of students test score and performance. However, in many Nigerian classroom buildings, poor design and erratic power supply result in inadequate lighting. Issues such as improperly oriented buildings, window designs that block rather than enhance daylight penetration, and insufficient interior reflectance contribute to substandard or improper illumination (Ezetoha & Okeoma, 2020; Gregg, 2016). The effects of improper classroom lighting include repetitive behaviors, lack of concentration, visual disability, and discomfort or annoyance to some people (Jaen et al., 2005) and these affect learning negatively.

On the other hand, Nigeria's unstable power supply contributes to inadequate lighting as many classrooms rely on electrical grids (Ezetoha & Chukwulobe, 2020) that frequently experience outages (Ohajianya et al., 2014). Classroom with poor architectural designs that fail to optimize natural lighting are particularly affected, leading to periods of insufficient illumination that hinder learning. Additionally, reliance on generators as an alternative power source drives up operational costs and contributes to noise and air pollution (Ezetoha & Offor, 2024), further complicating the classroom environment.

Globally, the rising energy costs, resources scarcity, and the environmental damage caused by fossil fuel emissions have led to push for energy efficiency (Xie et al., 2017; Ohlan, 2015). In response, innovations in lighting technology, such as light-emitting diodes (LEDs) are now integrated in lighting due to their energy-saving potential. However, while these systems provide efficient lighting, many do not effectively manage the electrical power supply, resulting in suboptimal energy savings. In addition, current systems often fail to automatically switch OFF lights and appliances when they are not in use, leading to unnecessary energy consumption.

In order to address these challenges, this work aims to develop an efficient and reliable lighting and power management system. The system ensures that classroom's lighting level is maintained at 300 lux when daylight is insufficient and will automatically switch OFF lights, sockets, and appliances when classroom is unoccupied, optimizing both energy usage and illumination.

Literature Review

Classroom lighting in Nigeria

Most classrooms in Nigeria use only daylight except during cloudy periods (Ezetoha & Okeoma, 2020). However, most of these classrooms do not provide adequate illumination for learning (Ezetoha & Chukwulobe, 2020). The inadequate or improper lighting of classrooms in Nigeria is caused by poor

classroom lighting design; a combination of artificial lighting and daylighting design (Ezetoha & Chukwulobe, 2020). Improper daylighting design stems from improper building form and location, window design and poor interior design (Ezetoha & Okeoma, 2020). Improper artificial lighting design can stem from non-use of automatic lighting system such as SLS in classroom design.

Improper classroom lighting is recognized by poor or excessive lighting or lighting with glare or flicker. The effects of improper classroom lighting include repetitive behaviors (Shapiro, Roth, & Marcus, 2001), disability (disability glare) with symptom of decreased visual performance (Winterbottoma & Wilkinsb, 2009) and visual search performance caused by flicker (Jaen et al., 2005), and these affects learning negatively.

Proper classroom lighting design

The lighting design for proper illumination of classroom requires that the classroom has illuminance of 300 lux (ambient light) or 500 lux as the case me be, standard unified glare rating (UGR) value of 19, color rendering index (CRI) of at least 80%, illumination at any point is 300 lux (uniform brightness) and the lighting should be controllable. These requirements are based on indoor lighting standard (ENSTO, 2011). The lighting design for classrooms comprises of daylighting and artificial lighting (DiLouie, 2016; Ezetoha & Chukwulobe, 2020; Ezetoha & Okeoma, 2020; Tungstram, 2020). The lighting design makes use of natural light that is available and artificial light in addition when day light is insufficient to properly illuminate classroom.

An Integrated Classroom Lighting System (ICLS) is mainly used to achieve proper illumination of classrooms. In ICLS, lights are turned OFF during the day when daylight is sufficient to illuminate classroom and fully or partially turned ON when light is insufficient, light intensity reduced or dimmed during visual presentation using projector or when teacher wants to draw students' attention, and turned off when nobody is making use of light (DiLouie, 2016; Emerging Technologies, 2021). The integrated classroom lighting is achieved through smart or intelligent lighting system.

Smart lighting system

A smart lighting system (SLS) or intelligent lighting system includes control, communication, and interconnection abilities. Smart light is a light source with controllability of certain light quality/quantity properties (Soheilian et al., 2021). The SLS system consists of components such as motion or occupancy sensors, daylight sensors for adjusting the light intensity to the environment and/or the user's needs and one or more switches and lighting fixtures used in the traditional lighting system. Intelligent lighting systems are typical used in interior lighting (in classrooms, offices, and residential buildings) and outdoor lighting (Füchtenhans, Grosse, & Glock, 2019).

Smart lighting system enables flexible light control which can provide light depending on the user's requirements by adjusting the color and intensity of light. The sensors used in SLS enable automatic light control, which provides enhanced services in addition to reducing energy consumption (Karlicek,

2012). In addition, SLSs are sustainable and environmentally friendly due to longer-life components used in it, and flexible light control that helps to reduce light pollution. Usually, light pollution is responsible for wasted energy due to excessive or obtrusive artificial light caused by bad lighting design (Gallaway et al., 2010). Comfortable handling, easy usability, and individual adaption as well as the opportunity for integration into existing systems are important for high user acceptance of SLS (Füchtenhans et al., 2021). In addition, SLSs have the potential to stimulate humans via circadian rhythm regulation based on its human-centric lighting (HCL) approach, which can improve well-being (Oh et al., 2014).

Energy saving in smart lighting system

Light quality and energy efficiency improvement is the main characteristic of SLS. Due to the application of efficient technologies such as light emitting diodes (LEDs), the energy consumption of lighting can be reduced significantly, with the additional advantages of improved light quality (Füchtenhans et al., 2021). A basic control method used in SLS is sensor-based lighting. Motion, occupancy or other external factors can be detected by sensors, enabling the system to adapt lighting to the situation. In order to reduce energy consumption and light pollution in SLS, artificial light is only (fully) switched on if motion or occupancy is detected by the sensor systems. If the workplace or environment is empty, lighting is switched off or dimmed to a predefined lower level (Chung & Burnett, 2001). Daylight sensors are used to detect daylight to enable the system complement daylight with artificial light if required (Caicedo & Pandharipande, 2016; Gilani & O'Brien, 2018).

Smart lighting systems can save energy without compromising functionality or safety standards (Pandharipande & Caicedo, 2015; Kaminska & Ozadowicz, 2018) depending on the use case and user behaviour. Von Neida et al. (2001) reported that energy savings range from 17% to 60% for motion-based light control. On the other hand, Chew et al. (2017) reported that energy savings for daylight sensing is above 40%. Studies that examined combined motion and daylight sensors reported a wider range and higher average energy savings, from 13% (Higuera et al. 2015) to 73.2% (Nagy et al. 2016). These results imply that the savings depend on different internal and external factors, such as window size and orientation, available hours of sunshine, and occupant usage patterns (Chew et al., 2017).

Related work

The most innovative aspects of lighting in classrooms tend to focus on automated systems. Automated electronic systems for classroom lighting are mainly used in developed countries such as United States of America but in limited application. Studies or works on automated electronic systems for classroom lighting are limited. In one of the older works, Lee et al. (2015) developed a lighting control system for classrooms based on context awareness. The system was an intelligent lighting control system that recognized the locations and behaviors of the teacher and students automatically by means of sensors; grasps the current class context, and creates appropriate lighting environments accordingly. The

system was fully automated. LED lighting whose color temperature, intensity of illumination and ON/OFF switch are adjustable in addition to hybrid sensors for context-awareness were used in the design. The aim of developing the system was to improve learning efficiency in the classroom, but the result of the development showed that it was not achieved.

Davis and Wilkerson (2017) developed an LED tunable classroom lighting systems and installed them in three classrooms. The luminaires used in the system were 2 ft by 4 ft Lithonia Lighting BLT Series Tunable White LED luminaire and 2-lamp electronic ballasts. Each recessed fluorescent luminaire in the former installation was replaced with a 2 ft by 4 ft Lithonia Lighting. The Illuminance levels in the classrooms at maximum output met or exceeded recommendations for the typical visual tasks. The use of multiple sensors and color-tunable LED luminaire made this system to be costly.

In another work, Davis (2017) developed Next-Generation Integrated Classroom Lighting System (NICLS). The development was aimed at providing high efficacy lighting, full illuminance control, and white light tenability to improve the educational environments of facilities that focus on learners of all ages. The system was designed by educational professionals with the help of teachers. Direct/indirect pendant luminaires and troffers and controllers were used in the design. The system also incorporated daylight harvesting and occupancy sensing and user interface (UI) which is designed to accommodate the ability to shift modes quickly because teachers cannot get distracted in the classroom.

Schledermann et al. (2019) implemented a dynamic lighting in classrooms. The aim of the work was to demonstrate the use of lighting as a tool to structure and support teaching and learning activities by teachers. The lighting system consisted of dimmable LED luminaires, hybrid sensors and controllers. The drawback of this system is the use of multiple sensors and high cost of components and public power supply.

In recent work, Ezetoha and Chukwulobe (2020) designed a microcontroller-based artificial lighting system for classrooms with aim of providing classrooms in Nigeria with ambient light. The system consisted power supply, light sensing, control, switching, lighting, display and alarm units. The system had two sources of power supply, and this made it possible to provide regular supply of electricity. An AT89C51 microcontroller was used as the control unit and it coordinates the entire activities of the system. The lighting unit consisted of 16 NXTGen 600x600mm, 40W LED panel lights connected in three different ways (three sets of light) to the control unit through three different switching/relay circuits. Any set of light provided appropriate level of illumination depending on classroom illuminance. The system maintained classroom illuminance around 300 lux with negligible glare, and this helped to prevent excessive variation of illuminance that could reduce visual performance and cause discomfort.

The works reviewed showed that the artificial lighting systems designed for classrooms in Nigeria are the old manually operated systems that depend on public power supply to operate. On the other hand,

only few automated artificial classroom lighting systems have been designed and implemented in developed countries. These systems use one source of power supply and multiple sensors that make them to be costly and complex. The proposed system has only two sensors and dual power supply. The system ensures that classroom lighting level is maintained at 300 lux when daylight is insufficient and automatically disconnects power in classroom when unoccupied, optimizing both energy use and illumination.

Methodology

Top down design approach was adopted for designing the intelligent lighting and energy management system for Nigerian classrooms.

System Design and Analysis

The system design comprised of hardware system design and program design. The hardware system was designed via specification of design, conversion of the specification into a block diagram and drawing and simulation of circuit diagram while the program was designed via algorithm with the help of flowchart.

Design specification

Function: The system maintains classroom illumination level at 300 lux when natural light is insufficient, and automatically switches OFF lights and electrical appliances when there is no occupant in classroom. The system also maintains classroom illumination level at 200 lux during presentations such as project defense.

Target users: The target users are students and teachers in educational institutions in Nigeria including tertiary institutions, primary and secondary schools.

Materials: Low-cost, efficient and durable materials were used in this design. The materials include light sensor, occupancy sensor, 3.5 KVA solar inverter system, Arduino Nano board, dimmable LED panel lights, transformers, discrete components, relays and sockets.

Ergonomics/overall size: The circuit of the system will be housed in a 250 x 200 x 80mm plastic enclosure. The system requires public power supply in addition to a 3.5 KVA solar power supply to ensure regular power supply and will operate only when it is switched ON.

Design process: The system was designed via specification of design, conversion of the specification into a block diagram and drawing and simulation of circuit diagram.

Equipment/tools-requirements: Software tools such as Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) and Proteus professional simulation software were used while designing the system.

System life span: The system will last for 5 to 10 years.

System block diagram

The system consists of power supply unit, sensing unit, control unit, lighting unit, appliance unit, display unit and alarm unit as shown block diagram of figure 1.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Intelligent Lighting and Energy Management System for Nigerian Classrooms

Power supply unit

Power supply unit provides electric power required by the components of the entire system. This unit supplies constant 220V power to LED panel lights, fans and sockets, 12V DC/30A relays and 5V DC to other components of the system. The power supply unit consists of 3.5 KVA solar rechargeable power system, public power source, automatic change over system/switch and regulated 5V supply system. The 3.5 KVA solar power is adequate for this design because the maximum load of the system is 2900W (KVA). The choice of components for the power supply unit was made based on the power requirements and carrying capacity calculated using guideline by (Theraja & Theraja, 2002; Toshiba, 2018).

Automatic change over system: Automatic change over system/switch consists of 220V/50Hz to 12V/500mA step-down transformer, 12V 1A bridge rectifier, 1000µf/35V capacitor, two 12V/30A relays and two IN4007 diodes. The transformer was selected for this design because the required rating of transformer was 220V/50Hz to 12V/500mA. The power output of the transformer (6W) is adequate for powering the relays that have maximum current requirement of 160mA each. The bridge rectifier is suitable for this design because a maximum current of 160mA (relay current) flows through it and it can withstand 2A. The 12V DC/30A relays are adequate for this design because they can withstand maximum load of 3600W; the maximum load of the system 2900W.

Regulated 5V supply system: The 5V DC power is provided through a regulated power supply circuit consisting of a 220V/50Hz to 12V/500mA step down transformer, a bridge rectifier, LM7805 voltage regulator, 1000µf/35V capacitor, LED indicator, and a 1K resistor that limits the voltage entering the LED. The 220V/50Hz input supply into the transformer is converted to 12V by transformer action and then passed through the rectifier which converts it to a DC voltage. The 1000µf capacitor filters the 12V DC while the LM7805 regulator regulates the voltage to 5V DC. The LM7805 voltage regulator is adequate for this design because the maximum current drawn by light sensor, occupancy

sensor, Arduino Nano board, LCD, buzzer and discrete components is less than 1A while its current rating is 3A.

Sensing unit

The sensing unit consists of light sensor and occupancy sensor and their interconnections.

Light sensor: The light sensor used in this design is GY-302 module; a calibrated digital light sensor. The GY-302 module is a BH1750 light sensor that senses the amount of ambient light and gives out the light intensity via the I2C interface. The sensor was selected for this work because it is Arduino-based sensor that can measure the light intensity between 0 lux and 65535 lux and has low operating voltage (3V to 5V DC). The sensor is suitable for this design in which the highest light intensity in classroom is less than 1000 lux.

Occupancy sensor: One HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor was used in this design for sensing presence of a student in the classroom (occupancy sensing). The sensor was selected for this work because it is Arduino-based sensor that can read distance from 2cm to 400cm (0.02m to 4.00m) with an accuracy of 0.3cm and has low operating voltage (5V DC). The sensor offers excellent non-contact range detection with high accuracy and stable readings and its operation is not affected by sunlight or black material. The sensor is suitable for this design in which the measurement is less than 0.5m. The HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor comes with ultrasonic transmitter and receiver modules and gives out signal in analog form. The ultrasonic sensor is meant to be fixed a distance of 20cm to the position of a student in front of the classroom (occupancy position).

Control unit

An Arduino Nano was used as the control unit in this design. The Arduino Nano is a small, complete, and breadboard-friendly board microcontroller board based on the ATmega328. The ATmega328 microcontroller contained in Arduino Nano processes and analyzes the input signals from sensors and gives instructions to other units in order to perform its function. Arduino Nano was chosen for this design because its input/output (I/O) pins are adequate for this design. It has operating voltage of 5V, 14 digital I/O pins (6 optional PWM outputs), 8 analog input pins, 32 KB flash memory, of which 0.5 KB is used by bootloader, 2 KB SRAM, 2 KB EEPROM and 16MHz clock speed. It requires 40mA DC per I/O pin and 50mA DC for 3.3 V pin. The Arduino Nano is equipped with 30 male I/O headers, in a DIP30-like configuration, which can be programmed using the Arduino software integrated development environment (IDE), and running both online and offline.

Switching unit

The switching unit consists of three transistor switching circuits or relay circuits. The relay circuits were used for interfacing the LED panel lights, fans and sockets. These components cannot be interfaced directly to microcontroller because the operating voltage of each relay is 12V and is different from that of the microcontroller (5V). In this design (figure 3), a relay circuit consists of a 12V DC/30A relay, a

1N4007 diode connected across it, a BC547 transistor and a $1k\Omega$ resistor connected to the base of the transistor. The BC547 transistor was chosen for this design because it can carry the load (12V relay) comfortably. The collector continuous current of the transistor is 800mA and the load trigger current (nominal current) of the relay is 53.3mA (from the relay specification) and therefore, adequate for it. The choice of 12V DC/30A relay is in order because each relay can withstand load of 3600W while the maximum load is 1300W (power consumed by 20 laptops). In addition, the 5V of any output pin of the ATmega 2560 microcontroller is adequate for switching BC337 transistor connected to it because a minimum of 0.7V is required to bias it.

Lighting unit

The lighting unit consists of fifteen 600x600mm, 40W dimmable LED ceiling panel lights. The LED panel light was chosen for this design because it is energy efficient, eco-friendly, has long lifespan (more than 5 years when used on an average of 8 hours a day) and efficient light distribution, glare and color accuracy. The 40W LED panel light requires input voltage of 220V AC, and only uses 40W of power and outputs a maximum of 3400 lumens (lm). It also had color rendering index of over 80, beam angle of 120° and maintenance factor (MF) of 0.8. The LED light is therefore, suitable for this system since it is effective for academic tasks.

The number and the arrangement of the LED panel lights in the classroom of 11m x 7.6m were determined based on guidelines by CharlstonLights (2016) and Parmar (2014). The required number of luminaires is $13.97 \approx 14$, so 15 was used since 14 cannot be arranged in equal proportion. The 15 luminaires produce the required uniform brightness of 300 lux (when fully switched ON) without daylight. The minimum spacing between luminaires along the width of the classroom is 2.4456m (2.5m was used), number of LED panel lights in each row is 5, axial spacing between each LED panel light is 2.2m, and the transverse spacing between each LED panel light is 2.533m. The 15 lights are connected in parallel and to 220V AC power supply at connection point A. The connection and arrangement of the 15 LED panel lights in the classroom ceiling is as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Connection and Arrangement of 15 LED Panel Lights in the Classroom Ceiling

Appliance unit

The appliance unit consists of 6 electric fan and 40 sockets and their interconnections. The sockets are meant to be used for at most 20 laptops and 20 smart phones in the classroom. Each of the 6 ceiling fans has power rating of 100W (total maximum power consumption is 600W). Each of the 20 laptops has power rating of 65W (total maximum power consumption is 1300W) and each of the 20 smart phone chargers has power rating of 20W (total maximum power consumption is 400W).

Display unit

A 2 x16 Liquid-Crystal Display (LCD) module was used as the display unit. This unit displays illumination level of classroom. The 2x16 LCD was chosen for this design because it displays meaningful information onto its screen, requires +5V power supply and can display 16 characters in each of the 2 rows at any instance of time.

Alarm unit

The alarm unit consists of a 5V buzzer with its interconnection components. The buzzer beeps for 60 seconds whenever the lights are on and nobody is detected in the occupancy position so that any student in the class will take the occupy position. The 5V buzzer was chosen because of its low input voltage range of 3V to 8V and 40mA current requirements, 80dB at 0.2 m sound output, and easy of connection to systems.

Schematic circuit diagram of the system

The circuit diagram of the intelligent lighting and energy management system for classrooms in Nigeria is as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Circuit Diagram of Intelligent Lighting and Energy Management System for Classrooms in Nigeria. The circuit diagram was first drawn by hand and authenticated (simulated) using Proteus 8.4 professional software.

Program design

The program design is a technical blueprint of how the proposed system will work. A flowchart and algorithm were used during the designing phase so as to understand the operational sequence of processing that must be followed. The flowchart helped in representing the various logical steps or algorithms involved in the program. The system program directs all the activities of the system including sensing, analysis of the sensed data, displaying of the measured values, switching of lights and appliances and triggering of alarm.

The system algorithm: The algorithm of the system for normal classroom activity is:

First configure microcontroller pins A6, A7, 2 and 3 input pins and pins 5, 6 to 11 as output pins.

Now initialize the LCD module.

Read in occupant distance (between 5m and 20m) into microcontroller through pins 2 and 3.

If occupant is not detected, don't supply power to fans and sockets.

If occupant is detected, supply power to fans and sockets via pins 5, 6 and 7, then read illuminance into microcontroller through pins A6 and A7.

If illuminance is equal to or greater than 300lux, read illuminance into microcontroller through pins A6 and A7.

If illuminance is not equal to 300lux, switch ON lights and dim till illuminance is maintained 300lux and switch OFF lights when daylight is equal to or greater than 300lux.

Read in occupant distance into microcontroller through pins 2 and 3.

If occupant is not detected, sound alarm for 60 seconds, then switch OFF lights and stop power supply to appliances via pins 5, 6 and 7.

Then read in occupant distance into microcontroller through pins 2 and 3.

This operation continues until the system is switched OFF via its power switch.

Operation of the system

The system performs its function based on the system program. When the system is switched ON, the occupancy sensor senses presence of occupant. If student or occupant is not detected, it continues to sense presence of occupant. If student is detected, the microcontroller sends signal to the relay circuits to supply power to the fans' and the sockets' through power connections points **B** and **C** respectively. The light sensor then senses daylight. If daylight is equal to or greater than 300 lux, lights are not switched ON, and the sensor continues sensing daylight. If daylight is less than 300 lux, lights are switched ON, and dimmed to maintain the illuminance at 300 lux. The light sensor continues to sense light in the classroom and adjust its levels via dimming until daylight is up to 300 lux.

The occupancy sensor also continues to sense presence of occupant. If occupant is detected, the occupancy sensor continues its sensing. If occupant is not detected, the microcontroller sends signal to the buzzer to sound alarm for 60 seconds to inform students to occupy the occupancy position if any of them is present in classroom. If no student occupies the position after 60 seconds, the system switches

OFF lights and appliances and starts and continues sensing presence of occupant. When occupant is detected, the system switches ON lights and appliances and starts the operation all over.

The system is also switched to the presentation mode during presentation such as project defense. In this case, the system performs its normal operation but maintains classroom illuminance at 200 lux.

Conclusion

The intelligent lighting and energy management system for Nigerian classrooms has been fully designed in this work. The system maintains illumination in a classroom at 300 lux when students or occupant is present and manages electric power used in the classroom.

The system's components include 3.5KVA solar power system and public power supply, regulated 5V power supply. Arduino Nano board, GY-302 light sensor, an HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor (occupancy sensor), transistor-based switching circuit, LED dimmable panel lights, sockets, fans and LCD. The system provides appropriate light to supplement daylight whenever classroom illuminance is less than 300 lux by automatically switching ON and adjusting electric lights. The system switches OFF lights when classroom's illuminance from daylight is up to 300 lux.

The system prevents excessive variation of illuminance that can reduce visual performance and cause discomfort and health disorders since it maintains classroom illuminance at 300 lux. The system also effectively manages electric power supplied to a classroom by automatically switching OFF light, appliances and sockets when they are not in use.

Recommendations

- i. The designed system can be implemented and adopted for use in Nigerian classrooms.
- ii. The technology used in this system can also be used in office and industrial lighting in order to prevent excessive variation of illuminance that can reduce visual performance and cause discomfort and health disorders.
- iii. This system can be modified to include colored lighting by incorporating colored lighting regimes in the system.
- iv. CCTV technology can be integrated in this system for occupancy sensing to enhance capturing of presence of students and to eliminate the needing for a student to occupy the occupancy position before his presence can be detected.

References

Caicedo, D., & Pandharipande, A. (2016). Daylight and occupancy adaptive lighting control system: An iterative optimization approach. *Light. Res. Technol.*, 48 (6), 661-675. DOI: 10.1177/1477153515587148

CharlstonLights. (2016). Deciding LED light quantity – how many is much? <http://www.charlstonlights.com/blog/led-light-quantity-how-many-much>

Michigan Journal of Engineering and Technology

Volume 14 Issue 1, January – March 2026

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 7.83

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MJET>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- Chew, I., Karunatilaka, D., Tan, C. P., & Kalavally, V. (2017). Smart lighting: The way forward? Reviewing the past to shape the future. *Energy and Buildings*, 149, 180–191.
- Chung, T. M., & Burnett, J. (2001). On the prediction of lighting energy savings achieved by occupancy sensors. *Energy Engineering*, 98(4), 6–23.
- Davis, J. L. (2017). Luminaires for advanced lighting in education. Research Triangle Institute (RTI) International, Project No. 02014911.
- Davis, R. G., & Wilkerson, A. (2017). Tuning the light in classrooms: Evaluating trial LED lighting systems in three classrooms at the Carrollton-farmers branch independent school district in Carrollton, TX. U.S. Department of Energy Solid-State Lighting Program.
- DiLouie, C. (2016). Lighting controls for today's classroom. <https://lightingcontrolsassociation.org/2016/11/21/lighting-controls-for-todays-classroom/>
- Dyck, J. (2002). The built environment's effect on learning: Applying current research. *Montessori Life*, 14(1), 53–56.
- Emerging Technologies. (2021). Integrated classroom lighting system. <http://e3tnw.org/ItemDetail.aspx?id=133>
- ENSTO. (2011). the indoor lighting standard, SFS-EN 12464-1:2011. <https://www.ensto.com/support/tools/lighting-guide/the-indoor-lighting-standard-sfs-en-12464-12011/>
- Ezetoha F. C., & Chukwulobe E. E. (2020). Microcontroller-based artificial lighting system for classrooms. *International Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 6 (6), 1-10.
- Ezetoha, F. C. & Offor, N. F. (2024). Classroom's indoor environmental condition: Influence on academic achievements and methods of maintaining optimum condition. In *Proceedings of School of Business Studies 2nd International Conference, Federal Polytechnic, Oko, 5th – 8th November, 2024*.
- Ezetoha, F. C., & Okeoma, G. (2020). Low-cost and safe lighting design for classrooms. *International journal of Advanced Research in ICT & Engineering*, 9(8), 1-14.

Michigan Journal of Engineering and Technology

Volume 14 Issue 1, January – March 2026

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 7.83

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MJET>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Füchtenhans, M., Grosse, E. H., & Glock, C. H. (2019). Use cases and potentials of smart lighting systems in industrial settings. *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 47(4), 101–107.

Füchtenhans, M., Grosse, E. H., & Glock, C. H. (2021). Smart lighting systems: State-of-the-art and potential applications in warehouse order picking. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(12), 3817-3839. DOI: 10.1080/00207543.2021.1897177

Gallaway, T., Olsen, R. N., & Mitchell, D. M. (2010). The economics of global light pollution. *Ecological Economics*, 69(3), 658–665.

Gilani, S., & O'Brien, W. (2018). A preliminary study of occupants' use of manual lighting controls in private offices: a case study. *Energy and Buildings*, 159, 572–586.

Gregg, D. A. (2016). Daylighting. <https://www.wbdg.org/resources/daylighting>

Halliwell, E., Main, L., & Richardson, C. (2007). The fundamental facts. Technical Report, Mental Health Foundation.

Higuera, J., Hertog, W., Perálvarez, M., Polo, J., & Carreras, J. (2015). Smart lighting system ISO/IEC/IEEE 21451 compatible. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 15(5), 2595–2602.

Jaen, M., Sandoval, J., Colombo, E., & Troscianko, T. (2005). Office workers' visual performance and temporal modulation of fluorescent lighting, *Leukos*, 1(4), 27–46.

Kaminska, A., & Ozadowicz, A. (2018). Lighting control including daylight and energy efficiency improvements analysis. *Energies*, 11(8), 2166.

Karlicek, R. F. (2012). Smart lighting-beyond simple illumination. *IEEE Photonics Society Summer Topical Meeting Series*, 147–148. IEEE. Seattle, WA, USA.

Lee, H., Kwon, S., Kim, K., Lee, K. & Lim, Y. (2015). An Implementation of a classroom lighting system for the improvement of learning efficiency, Conference: International Workshop on Learning Technology for Education in Cloud. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-22629-3_20

Nagy, J., Yong, F. Y., & Schlueter, A. (2016). Occupant centered lighting control: A user study on balancing comfort, acceptance, and energy consumption. *Energy and Buildings*, 126, 310–322.

Oh, J. H., Ji Yang, S., & Rag Do, Y. (2014). Healthy, natural, efficient and tunable lighting: Four-package white LEDs for optimizing the circadian effect, color quality and vision performance. *Light: Science & Applications*, 3(2), e141.

Ohajianya, A. C., Abumere, O. E., Owate, I. O., & Osarolube, E. (2014). Erratic power supply in Nigeria: Causes and solutions. *International Journal of Engineering Science Invention*, 3(7), 51-55.

Ohlan, R. (2015). The impact of population density, energy consumption, economic growth and trade openness on CO₂ emissions in India. *Natural Hazards* 79(2), 1409–1428.

Pandharipande, A., & Caicedo, D. (2015). Smart indoor lighting systems with luminaire-based sensing: a review of lighting control approaches. *Energy Build.* 104, 369-377.

Pandharipande, A., Caicedo, D., & Wang, X. (2014). Sensor-driven wireless lighting control: system solutions and services for intelligent buildings, *IEEE Sens. J.* 14 (12) 4207–4215. DOI: 10.1109/JSEN.2014.2351775.

Pandharipande, A., Rossi, M., Caicedo, D., Schenato, L., & Cenedese, A. (2015). Centralized lighting control with luminaire-based occupancy and light sensing. In *Proceedings of 2015 IEEE 13th International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN)*, 31–36. DOI: 10.1109/INDIN.2015.7281706.

Parmar, J. (2014). An example of calculating the number of indoor lighting fixtures. *Electrical Engineering*. <http://electrical-engineering-portal.com/an-example-of-calculating-the-number-of-indoor-lighting-fixtures>

Schledermann, K., Pihlajaniemi, H., Sen S., & Hansen, E. K. (2019). Dynamic lighting in classrooms: A new interactive tool for teaching. In: Brooks A., Brooks E., Sylla C. (eds) *Interactivity, Game Creation, Design, Learning, and Innovation. ArtsIT 2018, DLI 2018*. Lecture notes of the Institute for Computer Sciences, Social Informatics and Telecom.

Shapiro, M., Roth, D., & Marcus, A. (2001). The effect of lighting on the behavior of children who are developmentally disabled. *Journal of International Special Needs Education*, 4, 19–23.

Soheilian, M., Fischl, G., Aries, M. (2021). Smart lighting application for energy saving and user well-being in the residential environment. *Sustainability*, 13, 6198. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116198>

Michigan Journal of Engineering and Technology

Volume 14 Issue 1, January – March 2026

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 7.83

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MJET>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Theraja, B. L & Theraja, A. K. (2002). Electrical Technology (23rd ed.). S.chand.

Tigerlight. (2013). what lighting levels do I need? <https://www.tigerlight.com.au/resources/what-lighting-levels-do-i-need/>

Toshiba. (2018). Basic characteristics and application circuit design of transistor couplers. Photocoupler Application Note. Toshiba Electronic Devices & Storage Corporation. https://toshiba.semicon-storage.com/info/application_note_en_20180201_AKX00788.pdf?did=13438

Tungsrām, (2020). This is what ideal classroom lighting should look like. <https://tungsram.com/en/news/this-is-what-ideal-classroom-lighting-should-look-like>

Von Neida, B., D. Manicria, and A. Tweed. (2001). an analysis of the energy and cost savings potential of occupancy sensors for commercial lighting systems. Journal of the Illuminating Engineering Society, 30(2), 111–125.

Winterbottoma, M, & Wilkinsb, A. (2009). Lighting and discomfort in the classroom. Journal of Environmental Psychology, 29, 63–75.

Xie, R., Fang, J., & Liu, C. (2017). The effects of transportation infrastructure on urban carbon emissions. Applied Energy, 196, 199–207.